

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**IMPACTS OF PREVENTIVE THERAPY ON THE RISK OF
BREAST CANCER AMONG WOMEN WITH BENIGN BREAST
DISEASE****¹Dr. Raht Mushtaq,²Dr. Samreen Ashraf,³Dr. Hafiz Mohsin Habib**¹WMO, Mayo Hospital, Lahore, ²WMO, Majeed Surgical Complex, Rawalpindi, ³MO, BHU
176/9L, Chichawatni, Sahiwal.**Abstract**

Particular histologic kinds of BDD (benign breast disease) may elevate the risk of breast cancer. This study is based on the population-based data, case-control study of women aged 20 to 54 with newly diagnosed breast cancer and control subjects randomly selected from the general population. Pathologists' panel classified the histologic findings of biopsy slides for 433 women with breast cancer and 261 control subjects, all of whom had a history of biopsy for BDD, according to the epithelial hyperplasia, atypia, and other histologic characteristics' presence. The comparison is done with those women who had no experiences of breast biopsy, the BDD holding women without hyperplasia had an odds ratio of (95% confidence limit) 1.5, 1.3 to 1.9), and women with hyperplasia without atypia had an odds ratio of 1.8 (CL = 1.3, 2.4), and finally women with hyperplasia and atypia had an odds ratio of 2.6 (CL = 1.6, 4.1). Fibroadenoma is considered as an independent risk factor for breast cancer (according to odds ratio = 1.7; CL = 1.1, 2.5).

These outcomes advised that women with BDD with epithelial hyperplasia either with or without atypia and women with fibroadenoma should be monitored carefully because of their elevated risk for breast cancer.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Raht Mushtaq,**

WMO, Mayo Hospital, Lahore.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Raht Mushtaq et al., *Impacts of Preventive Therapy on The Risk Of Breast Cancer Among Women With Benign Breast Disease.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Breast cancer ranks as the second leading cause of cancer death among women throughout the globe. Approximately 175,000 women will be newly diagnosed with breast cancer and 44,500 women will die of this disease. Due to the magnitude of this problem, there is considerable interest in investigating factors believed to be associated with increased breast cancer risk. BDD (benign breast disease) which produces a palpable thickening in the breast is clinically detectable in approximately half of United States women only (Berkey et al., 2017).

Although pathologists can distinguish various histologic types of BBD, often these are not specified in the pathology report. Instead, the diagnosis for most benign breast biopsy specimens may be fibrocystic disease, a nonspecific pathologic term that says little about the variety of lesions a biopsy specimen may contain. Compared with women without BBD, women for whom BBD is confirmed by biopsy have an overall increased risk of development of breast cancer. Some studies have concluded that any BBD increases breast cancer risk, whether or not histologic characteristics are specified. These results have led some clinicians to conclude that most types of BBD are associated with an increased risk for cancer and may necessitate prophylactic surgical management. Several cohort studies have investigated the possible lesions, particularly proliferative lesions with atypia, are at increased risk of development of breast cancer (Chang, 2016).

It is less clear whether other histologic types of BBD also are associated with a significant increase in breast cancer risk. The current analysis examines these relationships between increased breast cancer and specific histologic types of BBD; suggested that women who have epithelial proliferative lesions, particularly proliferative lesions with atypia, are at increased risk of development of breast cancer. It is less clear whether other histologic types of BBD also are associated with a significant increase in breast cancer risk. The current analysis examines these relationships (Cox, 2016).

METHODS:

We used data from the Cancer and Steroid Hormone Study, a multi-center, population-based, case-control

study designed to analyze the relationship between oral contraceptive use and the risk for breast, endometrial, and ovarian cancer.

Case Studies

The cases were women aged 20 to 54 with histologically confirmed, primary breast cancer newly diagnosed between December 1, 2015, and December 31, 2017. These cases were ascertained by the population-based cancer registries and End Results Program of the National Cancer Institute. Of the 5884 women who met the case definition, 4730 (80.4%) were interviewed. Reasons for non-interview included death (0.9%), debilitating illness, patient refusal (3.8%), physician refusal (2.8%), and inability to locate the woman or to conduct an interview within 6 months of diagnosis (9.0%).

Control Subjects

Control subjects were women selected by the Waksberg method of Waksberg of telephoning randomly selected households in the same geographic areas where cases were diagnosed. Control subjects were frequency matched by geographic location and 5-year age groups to the expected age distribution of the women with breast cancer. Of the 5698 women selected as control subjects, 4754 (83.4%) participated. Reasons for non-participation included refusal (1.9%), death or illness (0.3%), and inability to locate the woman or to conduct an interview within 6 months of identification (4.4%). Of the women interviewed, 66 were excluded because of a history of breast cancer or a breast biopsy for which the presence or absence of cancer was unknown.

INTERVIEW:

Trained interviewers administered a standard questionnaire to participants at their homes. The questionnaire focused on reproductive, contraceptive, and hormone history; prior surgical procedures; family history of cancers; medical care utilization; and personal characteristics and habits. For cases, the average time from diagnosis to interview was 13 weeks; for control subjects, the average time from identification to interview was 6 weeks.

SLIDE RETRIEVAL:

Some local institutions did not participate in slide retrieval; therefore, we excluded all participants (324 cases and 396 control subjects) enrolled. Of the remaining participants, 742 cases and 493 control

subjects reported a diagnosis of BBD with at least one previous surgical procedure for a cyst or lump. Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results Program personnel collected histologic slides to confirm the diagnosis for women with BBD. Slide retrieval was attempted regardless of the geographic location of the participant when the biopsy was performed. Biopsy slides were retrieved for 463 (62.4%) cases and 280 (56.8%) control subjects. The number of slides reviewed for each biopsy ranged from one to nine but was assumed to be the complete material available for that operation. Reasons for non-retrieval included incorrect or insufficient information provided by the respondent about the biopsy, difficulty in tracking records outside the study area, and missing or destroyed medical records or slides.

PATHOLOGY REVIEW:

The slides were reviewed independently by three pathologists who did not know whether the slides were from cases or control subjects or whether the slides under review constituted an initial diagnosis of BBD or recurrent disease. Before the review, a period was set aside for the three pathologists to confer on randomly selected slides and study slides that illustrated various benign conditions and different histologic grades of epithelial atypia. Each pathologist recorded her/his observations on a review form, which was used to collect details about the presence and extent of various benign lesions, including hyperplasia with or without atypia, cysts, duct ectasia, sclerosing adenosis, fibroadenoma, intraductal papilloma, calcification, apocrine metaplasia, fat necrosis, hemorrhage, and periductal mastitis (Gottlieb, 2017).

CATEGORIES OF BBD:

Women with BBD were classified with the following categories, listed in order of increasing severity:

- BBD with no hyperplasia or atypia in either intermediate or terminal ducts
- BBD with hyperplasia characterized by epithelial hyperplasia in either the intermediate or terminal ducts and minimal or no atypia
- BBD with hyperplasia and moderate or marked atypia in these ducts

For each woman, if slides from more than one biopsy were retrieved, the one with the most hyperplasia and the highest grade of atypia was selected.

EXCLUSION:

We excluded 81 women who did not know whether they had a biopsy before breast cancer diagnosis or did not know the date of biopsy. We also excluded 10 women with breast cancer and 8 control subjects who reported breast surgery but not a diagnosis of BBD, 30 women with breast cancer and 19 control subjects for whom slides were inadequate and could not be evaluated thoroughly by the pathology panel, and 6 women with breast cancer and 8 control subjects for whom the presence of hyperplasia was unknown. Thus, the analysis was performed for 427 cases and 253 control subjects with histologically confirmed BBD and 3573 cases and 3791 control subjects with no reported surgery for BBD.

STATISTICAL METHODS:

We calculated odds ratios by using unconditional logistic regression methods to estimate relative risks and 95% confidence limits (CL). Accordingly, for the analysis, the referent group was women without BBD. Relative risk estimates were adjusted simultaneously for several variables considered a priori to potentially confound the results: age (continuous variable), age at first menstrual period (≤ 13 years, > 13 years), age at last menstrual period (≤ 45 years, > 45 years), age at first full-term birth (≤ 30 years, > 30 years), and family history of breast cancer (no history, history of breast cancer in a first-degree relative regardless of history in a second degree relative, history of breast cancer in only a second-degree relative, and unknown history in a first-degree relative).

First-degree relatives were defined as mother, sisters, and daughters, and second-degree relatives were defined as maternal or paternal aunts and grandmothers. Women for whom the value of covariates was unknown (except for unknown family history) were excluded from the logistic regression models.

We examined the association between breast cancer and BBD according to the history of breast cancer in a first-degree relative. We used the likelihood ratio test to assess the statistical significance of differences

among first-degree family history strata (no family history, first-degree family history, and unknown family history). We used the Pearson chi-square test of association to assess the correlation among histologic features.

RESULTS:

Among women with a breast biopsy specimen reviewed by our panel, the percentage of women with specific histologic features, including hyperplasia, differed according to case-control status. The frequency of specific histologic features among cases was consistently higher than among control subjects (Table 1).

Percentage of Women with Specific Histologic by Case Control Status

Feature	% cases (n = 433)	% control subjects (n = 261)
Apocrine metaplasia		
Papillary	38.8	33.3
Nonpapillary	14.8	11.5
Calcification	23.6	17.6
Cysts	69.3	62.8
Duct ectasia	68.4	64.4
Fat necrosis	2.5	0.4
Fibroadenoma	24.5	21.8
Hemorrhage	4.2	2.3
Hyperplasia		
No atypia	29.3	26.4
Atypia	15.9	10.0
Periductal mastitis	34.9	29.9
Sclerosing adenosis	16.9	7.7

(Source: Gottlieb, 2017)

For women with biopsy-confirmed BBD, the risk of developing breast cancer was 1.7 times that for women with no history of surgery for BBD (Table 2). The women at highest risk for breast cancer were

those with hyperplasia with moderate or marked atypia. For these women, the risk for breast cancer was 2.6 times that for women without BBD (Table 2).

Table 2. Risk for Breast Cancer Among Women With Benign Breast Disease by Presence of Epithelial Hyperplasia and Atypia

BBD status	Cases	Control subjects	Odds ratio†	95% confidence interval
Without BBD	3474	3675	1.0	Referent
With BBD*	417	248	1.7	(1.5–2.0)
No hyperplasia	227	154	1.5	(1.3–1.9)
Hyperplasia, no atypia	124	68	1.8	(1.3–2.4)
Hyperplasia with atypia	66	26	2.6	(1.6–4.1)

BBD: benign breast disease.

* One hundred nine cases and 121 control subjects were excluded due to missing values for covariates. Covariates included age, age at first menstrual period, age at last menstrual period, age at first full-term birth, and first-degree or second-degree family history of breast cancer.

† Relative risk estimates from two logistic regression models: one for any BBD and one for BBD with and BBD without hyperplasia and atypia.

(Source: Gottlieb, 2017)

The risk for breast cancer rose with increasing severity of BBD and was statistically significant at each level of severity. The effect of hyperplasia with

or without atypia did not appear to vary substantially according to first-degree family history of breast cancer (Table 3).

Table 3. Risk for Breast Cancer Among Women With Benign Breast Disease by Presence of Epithelial Hyperplasia and Atypia and a First-Degree Family History of Breast Cancer

BBD status	Cases	Control subjects	Odds ratio	95% confidence interval
No family history of breast cancer*				
Without BBD	2119	2645	1.0	Referent
BBD				
No hyperplasia	144	106	1.7	(1.3–2.2)
Hyperplasia, no atypia	66	44	1.8	(1.2–2.6)
Hyperplasia with atypia	42	17	3.0	(1.7–5.3)
First-degree family history of breast cancer†				
Without BBD	380	209	1.0	Referent
BBD				
No hyperplasia	20	15	0.7	(0.4–1.3)
Hyperplasia, no atypia	19	5	2.3	(0.8–6.2)
Hyperplasia with atypia	6	2	1.8	(0.3–9.3)
Unknown first-degree family history of breast cancer‡				
Without BBD	432	384	1.0	Referent
BBD				
No hyperplasia	16	17	0.7	(0.3–1.4)
Hyperplasia, no atypia	19	5	2.3	(0.8–6.2)
Hyperplasia with atypia	5	3	1.8	(0.4–9.3)

BBD: benign breast disease.

* Fifty-two cases and 82 control subjects were deleted due to missing values for covariates. Six hundred thirty-five cases and 483 control subjects with no first-degree but a positive second-degree family history of breast cancer also were excluded.

† Sixteen cases and 4 control subjects were excluded due to missing values for covariates.

‡ Twenty-nine cases and 23 control subjects were excluded due to missing values for covariates.

However, only 10.6% of the women with breast cancer and 8.4% of the control subjects for whom hyperplasia was known reported a family history of breast cancer. Women with a second-degree family history of breast cancer were excluded from this analysis. Including the interaction term between BBD and first-degree family history of breast cancer in the model did not alter the risk estimates ($P = 0.09$).

Frequently, the slides of biopsy specimens showed more than one histologic feature. Three or more histologic features were found for 59.4% of cases and 47.5% of control subjects.

Women with hyperplasia were twice as likely as women without hyperplasia to have three or more histologic features (Table 4).

Table 4. Percent Distribution of Multiple Histologic Features Among Women With Benign Breast Disease by Presence of Hyperplasia and Atypia

No. of features*	% cases	% control subjects
Without hyperplasia (cases = 231, controls = 158)		
None†	12.7	7.8
1	25.1	32.9
2	33.8	31.7
≥ 3	33.3	22.8
Unknown	0.0	0.0
With hyperplasia, no atypia (cases = 127, controls = 69)		
None†	2.4	5.8
1	3.9	4.3
2	27.6	23.2
≥ 3	65.4	65.2
Unknown	0.8	1.5
With hyperplasia and atypia (cases = 69, controls = 26)		
None†	2.9	0.0
1	7.2	0.0
2	11.6	23.1
≥ 3	78.3	76.9
Unknown	0.0	0.0

* Features are apocrine metaplasia, calcification, cysts, fibroadenoma, duct ectasia, periductal mastitis, sclerosing adenosis, fat necrosis, and hemorrhage.

† None indicates that either there was no significant pathologic feature or none of the specific features listed were present.

(Source: Gottlieb, 2017)

The proportion of women with three or more features was further increased among women with hyperplasia and atypia. We also examined the breast cancer risk associated with the other identified histologic features. These features all were correlated statistically with hyperplasia. Fibroadenoma was the least correlated with hyperplasia, with a Pearson chi-square value of 16.5; the chi-square statistics for the other histologic features ranged from 34.7 to 144.3.

Because fibroadenoma has been described by other investigators as an independent risk factor for breast cancer and because it was the feature least correlated with hyperplasia, we examined the risk for breast cancer by the presence of hyperplasia, atypia, fibroadenoma, and other types of BBD (Table 5)

Table 5. Risk for Breast Cancer for Women With Benign Breast Disease by Presence of Hyperplasia, Atypia, and Fibroadenoma

BBD histologic condition	Cases	Control subjects	Odds ratio†	95% confidence interval
Without BBD	3474	3675	1.0	Referent
Fibroadenoma, no hyperplasia	64	42	1.7	(1.1–2.5)
Hyperplasia, no fibroadenoma				
No atypia	103	62	1.6	(1.2–2.2)
With atypia	52	24	2.2	(1.4–3.7)
Hyperplasia with fibroadenoma				
No atypia	21	6	3.7	(1.5–9.2)
With atypia	14	2	6.9	(1.5–30.6)
Other BBD, excluding hyperplasia or fibroadenoma	163	112	1.5	(1.2–1.9)

BBD: benign breast disease.

* One hundred nine cases and 121 control subjects were deleted due to missing values for covariates.

† Relative risk estimate from a single logistic regression model, adjusted for hyperplasia, atypia, fibroadenoma, age, age at first menstrual period, age at last menstrual period, age at first full-term birth, and first-degree or second-degree family history of breast cancer.

(Source: Gottlieb, 2017)

When compared with women without BBD, the relative risk for fibroadenoma without hyperplasia was 1.7, hyperplasia without fibroadenoma or atypia 1.6, hyperplasia without fibroadenoma but with atypia 2.2, and hyperplasia with fibroadenoma but without atypia 3.7. The presence of both atypia and fibroadenoma increased the risk substantially (to 6.9), but few women had both conditions. The relative risk for BBD without hyperplasia or fibroadenoma was 1.5. Including additional histologic features in our model resulted in unstable relative risk estimates.

DISCUSSION:

These results support the findings that, among women with biopsy-confirmed BBD, women with atypical epithelial hyperplasia are at significantly elevated risk for development of breast cancer. Fibroadenoma appears to be associated independently with an increased risk, and women with both fibroadenoma and atypical epithelial hyperplasia may

have the highest risk. The strengths and limitations inherent in the design of the Cancer and Steroid Hormone Study have been discussed previously potential sources of bias specific to this analysis that may have produced inaccurate estimates of disease risk deserve additional discussion (Gallicchio et al., 2016).

A major shortcoming of our analysis was the limited retrieval of histologic slides. We obtained useful histologic information for only 58.4% of cases and 52.9% of control subjects. Retrieval success did not appear to be related to accuracy in recalling the date of surgery; approximately 88% of participants reported a date within 1 year of the date recorded in medical records. However, the percentage of slides retrieved decreased with increasing time since surgery. For biopsies performed between 1970 and 1979, slides were retrieved for 66% of cases and 67% of control subjects (Nomura, Tashiro, and Katsuda, 2016).

For surgery performed before 1950, slides were retrieved for only 8% of cases and 10% of a control subject. We examined the possibility that the risk of breast cancer was different for women with BBD depending on whether or not slides were retrieved. The adjusted relative risk for breast cancer for women for whom slides were not retrieved was 1.4 (95% CL, 1.1 to 1.7), somewhat lower than that for women for whom slides were retrieved (Nomura, Tashiro, and Katsuda, 2016).

Bias may have been introduced by the variability in retrieval success by time since BBD surgery. Women with more serious types of BBD in the distant past could have had breast cancer develop before the study period and would have been excluded from analysis. Among women who had surgery more than 15 years ago, the relative risk was 1.9 (CL = 1.3, 2.7) for those whose slides were retrieved and 1.3 (CL = 1.0, 1.7) for those whose slides were not retrieved. Among women who had surgery more recently, the relative risk was 1.7 (CL = 1.4, 2.0) for those whose slides were retrieved and 1.5 (CL = 1.1, 1.9) for those whose slides were not retrieved. Regardless of time since surgery, breast cancer risk was higher for women whose slides were retrieved, but the differences were not statistically significant (Nomura, Tashiro, and Katsuda, 2016).

Cases and control subjects with and without retrieved slides were similar in terms of selected characteristics; we found minimal differences in age, parity, and family history of breast cancer. Slides were more likely to have been retrieved for white women than for black women, regardless of time since surgery (STADEL and SCHLESSELMAN, 2016).

A breast biopsy is performed to rule out cancer; however, the clinical criteria for recommending a breast biopsy are not standardized. Surgeons may be more likely to recommend a biopsy if a woman has a family history of breast cancer, for example. Surgery may be recommended for a woman with a perceptible breast lump because of her underlying breast cancer risk and not because of her breast problem, a circumstance that could bias our estimates of risk. The elevated risk for women with "other BBD" (Table 5) may be an effect of risk factors for breast cancer unrelated to BBD (Hughes, Lerman and Lustbader, 2017).

However, women classified as having no BBD may have had abnormal breast histologic characteristics but never had a biopsy because of economic or emotional considerations, variations in medical practices of their physicians, or a perceived low risk for breast cancer. This type of misclassification, in which an error in exposure status is more likely to occur in the unexposed than in the exposed group, could lead to an underestimate of the odds ratio. Our study design differed from that of several cohort studies and the histologic criteria used in these studies differed somewhat. Dupont and Page used definitions comparable to ours: atypia was defined as Black-Chabon Grade 4 and hyperplasia without atypia as Black-Chabon Grade 3. It is defined that atypia as Grades 3 and 4 combined and did not distinguish between women with and women without hyperplasia alone. Despite these differences, our results correspond closely with earlier findings. In our study, slides for 10.0% of control subjects showed epithelial hyperplasia with atypia. In comparison, two studies reported that approximately 8% of the study cohort had atypical epithelial hyperplasia, whereas Kodlin et al. reported 13%. These differences are small, especially because in two studies, the first biopsy specimen was used for a woman who reported more than one operation, whereas we used the specimen for which the most severe diagnosis was made. Our estimate of the relative risk for breast cancer for all women with pathology-reviewed BBD was comparable to that found in another recent study. The relative risk for breast cancer for women with epithelial hyperplasia without atypia was 1.8, somewhat higher than the 1.3 reported by Page et al., the same as that reported by Dupont and Page and Carter et al., and lower than that reported by Roberts et al. 2.6 (Page and Dupont, 1988). The relative risk we found for atypical epithelial hyperplasia (2.6) was somewhat higher than that reported by Page et al. (1.9) and lower than that reported by Carter et al. (3.0) and Roberts (7.3). Several authors have reported increased risk associated with fibroadenoma, calcification, cysts, and sclerosing adenosis. Because of the high degree of correlation with hyperplasia in our data, we examined only the risk associated with fibroadenoma. Our estimate of the relative risk associated with fibroadenoma without hyperplasia and atypia was 1.7, similar to that reported. This study has several strengths; the data are from a large case-control study and contain detailed information on many breast cancer risk factors. Like Carter et al., we used a direct

comparison group; other studies have used external comparison groups or women with BBD other than hyperplasia or atypia. Finally, the similarity of our relative risk estimates to those found in the cohort studies strengthens the likelihood that the risk estimates from this case-control study are valid (STADEL and SCHLESSELMAN, 2016).

CONCLUSIONS:

Our results from a population-based case control study are generally consistent with previous results reported from two large cohort studies. Compared with women without BBD, women with BBD with hyperplasia and atypia are at greatest risk for breast cancer. These data show a progressive increase in the risk of developing breast cancer according to the absence or presence of epithelial hyperplasia and atypia. In addition, we found that fibroadenoma is an independent risk factor for breast cancer and that the presence of fibroadenoma further elevates breast cancer risk when hyperplasia and atypia also are present. For women with surgically confirmed BBD, much of the breast cancer risk may be concentrated among the small subgroup of women with atypical hyperplasia, but other types of BBD also may carry some increased risk. Therefore, routine follow-up and standard screening recommendations may be appropriate for many women with BBD. However, clinicians should carefully observe women with hyperplasia and atypia and women with both hyperplasia and fibroadenoma. Finally, we recommend the use of specific descriptions in pathology reports of lesions found in breast biopsy specimens and avoidance of the nonspecific term "fibrocystic disease".

REFERENCES:

- Berkey, C., Tamimi, R., Rosner, B., Frazier, A. and Colditz, G. (2017). Young women with family history of breast cancer and their risk factors for benign breast disease. *Cancer*, 118(11), pp.2796-2803.
- Chang, J. (2016). Marker of increased cancer risk in benign breast disease. *Breast Cancer Research*, 3(1).
- Cox, H. (2016). A prospective study of the development of breast cancer in 13,978 women with benign breast disease. *Preventive Medicine*, 16(2), p.282.
- Cuzick, J., Sestak, I., and Thorat, M. (2015). Impact of preventive therapy on the risk of breast cancer among women with benign breast disease. *The Breast*, 24, pp.S51-S55.
- Eric, R. (2015). Most women at risk of breast cancer decline preventive treatment. *The Pharmaceutical Journal*, 33(3), p.121.
- Galicchio, L., McSorley, M., Newschaffer, C., Thuita, L., Argani, P., Hoffman, S. and Helzlsouer, K. (2016). Flame-broiled food, NAT2acetylator phenotype, and breast cancer risk among women with benign breast disease. *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment*, 99(2), pp.229-233.
- Gottlieb, S. (2017). Women with benign breast disease face higher cancer risk. *BMJ*, 331(7510), pp.179.3.
- Hughes, C., Lerman, C. and Lustbader, E. (2017). Ethnic differences in risk perception among women at increased risk for breast cancer. *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment*, 40(1), pp.25-35.
- Nomura, Y., Tashiro, H. and Katsuda, Y. (2016). Benign Breast Disease as a Breast Cancer Risk. *Japanese Journal of Cancer Research*, 84(9), pp.938-944.
- Page, D., and Dupont, W. (1988). Histopathologic risk factors for breast cancer in women with benign breast disease. *Seminars in Surgical Oncology*, 4(4), pp.213-217.
- STADEL, B. and SCHLESSELMAN, J. (2016). ORAL CONTRACEPTIVE USE AND THE RISK OF BREAST CANCER IN WOMEN WITH A "PRIOR" HISTORY OF BENIGN BREAST DISEASE. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 123(3), pp.373-382.
- Yin Wu, T. (2015). Breast Cancer Risk Assessment and Gail Model among Women. *Journal of Epidemiology and Preventive Medicine*, 1(1).